

STOCHASTIC MODEL TO ESTIMATE THE AH ON CORTISOL PRODUCTION USING WEIBULL DISTRIBUTION

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Abstract:

The adrenal glands are the primary source of mineralocorticoids, glucocorticoids, and the so-called adrenal androgens. Under physiological conditions, cortisol and adrenal androgen synthesis are controlled primarily by ACTH. Although it has been established that ACTH can stimulate steroidogenesis, the effects of ACTH on overall gene expression in human adrenal cells have not been established. In this paper, we estimate the Adrenocorticotrophic Hormone on cortisol production using Weibull Distribution with the help of Gompertz Makeham function.

Key Words: Adrenocorticotrophic Hormone, Cortisol, Weibull Distribution & Gompertz Makeham Function.

1. Introduction:

ACTH is a 39 amino acid polypeptide predominantly synthesized in and secreted from the anterior lobe of the pituitary gland. The synthesis and secretion of ACTH are tightly controlled by the hypothalamic pituitary adrenal axis. Under stress conditions, the paraventricular nucleus of the hypothalamus secretes vasopressin and CRH. These two peptides regulate the anterior lobe of the pituitary gland and stimulate the secretion of ACTH. ACTH subsequently induces adrenal cortex expansion and corticosteroid production (mainly cortisol in humans). Once synthesized, cortisol in turn acts on the hypothalamus and pituitary (To suppress CRH and ACTH production) causing a negative feedback cycle. In the adrenal glands, ACTH acts by binding to specific cell surface ACTH receptors (Melanocortin 2 Receptor MC2R). MC2R is a seven membrane spanning G-protein coupled receptor that is primarily expressed in adrenocortical cells. Upon ligand binding, the receptor undergoes conformational changes that stimulate adenylyl cyclase, leading to an increase in intracellular cAMP and subsequent activation of protein kinase A (PKA).

Although previous studies have identified some ACTH responsive genes that are involved with the steroidogenic and growth related effects of ACTH [2-3], [6], [8-9], [11] & [18], there is a lack of knowledge regarding the global actions of ACTH on gene expression. Given the critical role of ACTH in adrenal development, steroidogenesis, and disease, it is appropriate to further define the detailed effects of ACTH on human adrenal cell gene expression. In this paper the problem is investigated by the hazard function of [19]. Among the useful functions applicable to real life data and the logit of beta distribution are the Beta Pareto [1]; Beta Laplace [7]; Beta Weibull[5]; Beta Normal [4]; Beta Gumbel [10]. Also we estimate the Adrenocorticotrophic Hormone on cortisol production using Weibull Distribution with the help of Gompertz Makeham function.

2. Bio Mathematical Model:

The Gompertz Makeham function is a distribution that gives very good approximations to empirical distributions of life length not only for human populations but also for different biological arts. There will be investigations of some properties of the Gompertz Makeham distribution.

The Gompertz Makeham distribution has the survival function:

$$\bar{F}_\psi(m) = \exp\left[-am - b \frac{e^{cm} - 1}{c}\right] \tag{1}$$

Where m is life time always non-negative ($m \geq 0$) and a, b and c are known non negative parameters and $a + bc > 0$ and hence

$$\bar{F}_\psi(m) > 0 \text{ for } m > 0 \text{ and } \bar{F}_\psi(0) = 1 \tag{2}$$

How different values of this three parameters influence to the model will be researched. In general the hazard function of the Gompertz Makeham distribution often can be used to express the behavior of the distribution.

The cumulative hazard function of a distribution can be defined by the relation

$$H_\psi(m) := \ln\left(\frac{1}{\bar{F}_\psi(m)}\right), \quad \psi = (a, b, c) \tag{3}$$

And the intensity hazard function is the derivative of the cumulative hazard function

$$h_{\psi}(m) := \frac{dH_{\psi}(m)}{dm} \quad (4)$$

The Gompertz Makeham distribution has the cumulative hazard function

$$H_{\psi}(m) = am + b \frac{e^{cm} - 1}{c} \quad (5)$$

And the intensity hazard function is

$$h_{\psi}(m) = a + be^{cm}. \quad (6)$$

Formulas (5) and (6) can easily be derived from its survival function (1) and the definitions of the hazard function (3) and (4). Note that $H_{\psi}(m) > 0$ is $m > 0$ due to (2).

Another property that can be derived is the probability density function of the Gompertz Makeham function

$$f_{\psi}(m) = \frac{dF_{\psi}(m)}{dm} = \frac{d(1 - e^{-H(m)})}{dm} = h_{\psi}(m) e^{-H(m)} = (a + be^{cm}) \exp \left[- \left(am + b \frac{e^{cm} - 1}{c} \right) \right]. \quad (7)$$

It will be of interest if there exists any points of extremum not at the boundary of the probability density function of the Gompertz Makeham distribution. This knowledge is necessary for the possibility to conclude if the probability density function of the Gompertz Makeham distribution is unimodal or not. The probability density function is unimodal if the derivative is 0 for at most one value of the derivative. The derivative of the probability density function (7) of the Gompertz Makeham distribution is

$$\frac{df_{\psi}(m)}{dm} = \frac{d(h_{\psi}(m)e^{-H(m)})}{dm} = (h'_{\psi}(m) - h^2_{\psi}(m)) = ((cbe^{cm}) - (a + be^{cm})^2) e^{-H(m)} \quad (8)$$

Because as stated in expression (6) the intensity hazard function of the Gompertz Makeham distribution is $h_{\psi}(m) = a + be^{cm}$ and therefore the derivative of it is $h'_{\psi}(m) = cbe^{cm}$.

Right hand side of equation (8) is 0 only when the statements $(cbe^{cm}) = (a + be^{cm})^2$ is true, because $0 < H(m) < \infty$ and $e^{-H(m)} > 0$. There exists one or two points of extremum only when $(cbe^{cm}) = (a + be^{cm})^2$ and the values of the life length that gives this equality are positive.

Set $x = be^{cm}$, then (8) can be written as

$$cx = (a + x)^2 = a^2 + 2ax + x^2 \text{ or } x^2 = (c - 2a)x - a^2.$$

The value x can be solved by a second grade equation so the roots are

$$x_1 = \frac{c}{2} \left(1 - \sqrt{1 - \frac{4a}{c}} \right) - a \text{ and } x_2 = \frac{c}{2} \left(1 + \sqrt{1 - \frac{4a}{c}} \right) - a$$

and in time scale

$$m_1 = \frac{1}{c} \ln \left(\frac{1}{b} \left(\frac{c}{2} \left(1 - \sqrt{1 - \frac{4a}{c}} \right) - a \right) \right), \quad (9)$$

$$m_2 = \frac{1}{c} \ln \left(\frac{1}{b} \left(\frac{c}{2} \left(1 + \sqrt{1 - \frac{4a}{c}} \right) - a \right) \right). \quad (10)$$

As earlier defined a, b and $c \geq 0$. We have $m_1 \leq m_2$, otherwise the solution is a natural logarithm of a negative value, which is a complex value and for that case m_1 and m_2 will have complex time. This fact makes sure that the points of extremum occur at non-negative time if they exist. If m_1 is positive there are two possibilities. Either there exist both a local minimum and a local maximum of the probability density function or there exist an inflection point and there doesn't exist any other point of extremum separated from the boundary of the function, occurs if $m_1 = m_2$. If m_1 is not positive and m_2 is positive then there exist only a local maximum of the density probability function. If m_2 is not positive there are no points of extremum for the

probability density function of the Gompertz-Makeham distribution. The function is unimodal if there are no local maximum not at the boundary of the function.

3. Example:

Figure (1) Time dependent effects of ACTH on cortisol production in human adult adrenal (AA) cells. Primary human AA cells were prepared as described under Materials and methods, and plated at the density of 2,00,000 cells per well in 24 well dishes. Cells were treated with or without ACTH (10nM) for the indicated times, and cortisol was quantified in the medium using EIA. Cortisol data were normalized to protein per well and expressed as the fold change over basal condition (untreated cells) for each time point. Results represent the mean \pm S.E.M. of data from at least three independent experiments. Three wells were analyzed for individual treatment in each experiment. Statistics were calculated using one way Anova followed by Dunnett’s test, comparing with baseline. $**P<0.01$ [12-17] & [20].

Figure (1): Effects of ACTH on cortisol production in human adult adrenal (AA) cells

Figure (2): Effects of ACTH on cortisol production in human adult adrenal (AA) cells using Weibull Distribution

4. Conclusion:

By applying a bio mathematical approach, we defined and estimate the genomic effects of ACTH in human adult and FA primary cultures. The newly defined adrenal ACTH responsive genes can provide clues to the mechanism of ACTH regulated steroidogenesis and cell growth, and may lead to further understanding of the global functions of ACTH in the adrenal gland. Gompertz Makeham function with Weibull distribution gives the same as the medical report. The medical reports are beautifully fitted with the mathematical model. Hence the mathematical report {Figure (2)} is coincide with the medical report {Figure (1)}.

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